

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: THUCH****FIRST NAME: JAMES****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Commonly in an essay writing, the three main structure of a paragraph includes;**

- Paragraph structure with a body and the conclusion.
- An introduction, the body and the conclusion.¹**
- An introduction, the body and the recommendation.
- The claims, the body of the message and the conclusion.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Peroid 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

2. (_____) is an academic crime when;

- A student paraphrase other people's ideas, or information appropriately with good citations.
- A student uses other people ideas or sources of information as his/her own without crediting the sources.²**
- A student cites or references all the consulted sources of information correctly.
- A student paraphrase other people's ideas, or information inappropriately with good citations.

3. According to Euclid University, students are encouraged to avoid citing a lot of;

- Primary sources, or articles.
- Secondary sources.
- Tertiary sources.³**
- Primary and secondary sources.

² Ibid., 34.

³ Kate L.Turabian, *A Manual for writers of Research Paper, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th Ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 37.

4. In academic writing practices, the reasons for citing other academic articles referred to is;

- To give credit to others and to show accuracy and facts/evident of no plagiarism by widely reading of articles.
- To give credit to others and to show accuracy and facts/evident by showing widely reading of articles.⁴**
- To give credit to others and to show accuracy and facts/evident that few journal articles are consulted.
- To give credit to others and to show accuracy and facts/evident to let readers know we are professional in writing articles.

5. In an introductory chapter of dissertation report, the errors are when chapter one does;

- Include the location/background of the study, the problem statement, the purpose, research questions and or design, main objectives and the aims and the significant of the research.

⁴ Ibid., 139.

- Not include the location/background of the study, the problem statement, the purpose, research questions, design, main objectives and the aims and the significance of the research.⁵**
- Include the location/background of the study, the problem statement, the purpose without research questions and or design including objectives and the significance of the research.
- Include the location/background of the study, the problem statement, the purpose without research questions and or design including objectives and the significant of the research.
- 6. According to research paradigm, a word postpositivist is applied as;**
- Postpositivist is used in qualitative design.
- Postpositivist is used in quantitative design.⁶**
- Constructivist is used in qualitative design.
- Constructivist is used in quantitative design.

- 7. In academic writing practices, theoretical and conceptual framework are used interchangeably but are commonly used as follow;**

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019), 74.

⁶ Ibid, 137.

Theoretical framework should be best with deductive design approach.⁷

Theoretical framework should be best with inductive design approach.

Theoretical framework should be best with inductive design approach.

Also, the theoretical/conceptual framework can be applied in both deductive and inductive approach.

8. **In aspect of qualitative research, trustworthy conclusion depends on;**

Creditability, dependability, confirmability, and transformability

Creditability, dependability, confirmability, and transferability.⁸

Creditability, dependability, confirmability, and generalization.

Validity, reliability, objectivity, and generalization of findings.

9. **Where does research principle allow positionality practices?**

In quantitative research

In qualitative research.⁹

Qualitative and quantitative research approach.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 397.

⁸ Ibid., 474.

⁹ Ibid., 153.

- Qualitative and quantitative research all involve positionality stance.

10. In general, different schools of thoughts could differently define a word research, but it is commonly defined as;

- A systematic inquiry of phenomena of concern in an institution or in the community.
- A process of systematic inquiry in order to response to questions or question of concern in an institution or in the community.¹⁰**
- A systematic inquiry in order to response to questions or questions of concern in an institution or in the community.
- A systematic inquiry in order to response to question or question of concern in an institution or in the community.

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Bloomberg, Linda D and Volpe M. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: Columbia University, 2019.

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¹⁰ Turabian, 19.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.